

Error in androguard python package #6

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We received an zlib.error: Error -3 while decompressing data: invalid distance too far back error in androguard while fuzzing.

@node0:~/droidbot$ python3 start.py -aa ../fuzzing_run_3/output/default/crashes/id:000000,sig:10,src:000016
INFO:Device:disable minicap on emulator
INFO:Device:disable minicap on sdk >= 32
INFO:androguard.apk:Starting analysis on AndroidManifest.xml
Traceback (most recent call last):
  File "/users/droidbot/droidbot/droidbot.py", line 96, in __init__
    self.app = App(app_path, output_dir=self.output_dir)
  File "/users/droidbot/droidbot/app.py", line 29, in __init__
    self.apk = APK(self.app_path)
  File "/users/.local/lib/python3.10/site-packages/androguard/core/bytecodes/apk.py", line 291, in __init__
    self._apk_analysis()
  File "/users/.local/lib/python3.10/site-packages/androguard/core/bytecodes/apk.py", line 311, in _apk_analysis
    manifest_data = self.zip.read(i)
  File "/usr/lib/python3.10/zipfile.py", line 1500, in read
    return fp.read()
  File "/usr/lib/python3.10/zipfile.py", line 932, in read
    buf += self._read1(self.MAX_N)
  File "/usr/lib/python3.10/zipfile.py", line 1022, in _read1
    data = self._decompressor.decompress(data, n)
zlib.error: Error -3 while decompressing data: invalid distance too far back
[CONNECTION] ADB is disconnected
[CONNECTION] DroidBotIme is disconnected
Traceback (most recent call last):
  File "/users/droidbot/droidbot/droidbot.py", line 96, in __init__
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  File "/users/droidbot/droidbot/app.py", line 29, in __init__
    self.apk = APK(self.app_path)
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    data = self._decompressor.decompress(data, n)
zlib.error: Error -3 while decompressing data: invalid distance too far back

During handling of the above exception, another exception occurred:

Traceback (most recent call last):
  File "/users/droidbot/start.py", line 196, in <module>
    main()
  File "/users/droidbot/start.py", line 167, in main
    droidbot = DroidBot(
  File "/users/droidbot/droidbot/droidbot.py", line 116, in __init__
    self.stop()
  File "/users/droidbot/droidbot/droidbot.py", line 191, in stop
    if hasattr(self.input_manager.policy, "master") and \
AttributeError: 'NoneType' object has no attribute 'policy'
@node0:~/droidbot$

```

crash greybox fuzzing Python androguard 15 minutes ago

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and another one:

@node0:~/droidbot$ python3 start.py -aa ../fuzzing_run_3/output/default/crashes/id:000003,sig:10,src:000005
INFO:Device:disable minicap on emulator
INFO:Device:disable minicap on sdk >= 32
INFO:androguard.apk:Starting analysis on AndroidManifest.xml
Traceback (most recent call last):
  File "/users/droidbot/droidbot/droidbot.py", line 96, in __init__
    self.app = App(app_path, output_dir=self.output_dir)
  File "/users/droidbot/droidbot/app.py", line 29, in __init__
    self.apk = APK(self.app_path)
  File "/users/.local/lib/python3.10/site-packages/androguard/core/bytecodes/apk.py", line 291, in __init__
    self._apk_analysis()
  File "/users/.local/lib/python3.10/site-packages/androguard/core/bytecodes/apk.py", line 311, in _apk_analysis
    manifest_data = self.zip.read(i)
  File "/usr/lib/python3.10/zipfile.py", line 1500, in read
    return fp.read()
  File "/usr/lib/python3.10/zipfile.py", line 932, in read
    buf += self._read1(self.MAX_N)
  File "/usr/lib/python3.10/zipfile.py", line 1036, in _read1
    self._update_crc(data)
  File "/usr/lib/python3.10/zipfile.py", line 964, in _update_crc
    raise BadZipFile("Bad CRC-32 for file %r" % self.name)
zipfile.BadZipFile: Bad CRC-32 for file 'AndroidManifest.xml'
[CONNECTION] ADB is disconnected
[CONNECTION] DroidBotIme is disconnected
Traceback (most recent call last):
  File "/users/droidbot/droidbot/droidbot.py", line 96, in __init__
    self.app = App(app_path, output_dir=self.output_dir)
  File "/users/droidbot/droidbot/app.py", line 29, in __init__
    self.apk = APK(self.app_path)
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    self._update_crc(data)
  File "/usr/lib/python3.10/zipfile.py", line 964, in _update_crc
    raise BadZipFile("Bad CRC-32 for file %r" % self.name)
zipfile.BadZipFile: Bad CRC-32 for file 'AndroidManifest.xml'

During handling of the above exception, another exception occurred:

Traceback (most recent call last):
  File "/users/droidbot/start.py", line 196, in <module>
    main()
  File "/users/droidbot/start.py", line 167, in main
    droidbot = DroidBot(
  File "/users/droidbot/droidbot/droidbot.py", line 116, in __init__
    self.stop()
  File "/users/droidbot/droidbot/droidbot.py", line 191, in stop
    if hasattr(self.input_manager.policy, "master") and \
AttributeError: 'NoneType' object has no attribute 'policy'
@node0:~/droidbot$

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